

***In silico* method to study immunotoxicity: PFAS case study**

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Abstract

Perfluorinated substances (PFAS) are a class of synthetic chemicals widely used in industry to which people and the environment are exposed. Human studies have shown that PFAS can cause immunosuppression, lower resistance to disease, and an increased risk of infections with a decreased response to vaccination. However, not much is known about the mechanism of action via which these substances act. Therefore, the aim of the project is to evaluate the immunotoxic effects of PFAS and identify underlying mechanisms through the design of new approach methodologies (NAMs)-based approaches. To reach these goals, an integrated testing strategy (ITS) consisting of *in vitro* and *in silico* methods was developed. Based on the *in vivo* evidence, suitable *in vitro* models were identified to evaluate parameters relevant to the immunotoxicity *in vivo*. The effects of PFAS on the most important immune cells were studied using only human models, and the results obtained with the selected NAMs support the *in vivo* evidence. Furthermore, mathematical fate and distribution models were used to identify the nominal concentration of PFAS in the *in vitro* cell system and physiologically based kinetics (PBK) modelling was used to perform quantitative *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (QIVIVE) to extrapolate *in vitro* effect concentrations to external doses. Moreover, the 'Universal Immune System Simulator' was used to complete the ITS and investigate the effects on vulnerable populations and predict the threshold dose for which we have an immunotoxic effect. This work will show the approach, with insight into the application of the *in silico* distribution models, to obtain an ITS, for the immunotoxicity of PFAS, in support of chemical risk assessment.

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